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Synthesis and Characterisation of Oxochromium(v) Dithiocarbamate Complexes

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IN the present work we report the preparation and characterisation of some oxochromium(v) complexes using diethyldithiocarbamate (dedtc), 4-morpholinyl dithiocarbamate (morpdtc), and piperidinyldithiocarbamate (pipdtc) as ligands.

Experimental

The chemicals employed were of laboratory grade. Dithiocarbamates derived from diethylamine, 4-morpholine and piperidine were prepared by conventional methods¹.

Preparation of complexes : Potassium dichromate (0.5 g) was dissolved in a mixture of 1:1 *N,N*-dimethylformamide and water (15 ml) and the solution was cooled to -10°, Concentrated HCl (1 ml) and calculated amount of hydrazinium chloride were then added to it with constant stirring, followed by the addition of a cold solution of

sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (4 g in 50 ml water). The resulting solid complex was filtered, washed with water and dried. 4-Morpholinyl dithiocarbamate and piperidinyldithiocarbamate complexes were prepared similarly and all the complexes were crystallised from chloroform-acetonitrile mixture.

Chromium, sulphur and nitrogen were estimated by standard analytical techniques². The electronic, ir and far-ir spectra were recorded on Shimadzu-uv-150-02, Shimadzu-IR-408 and Perkin-Elmer 983 G spectrophotometers, respectively. The epr spectra were recorded on a Varian '4 X-band spectrometer. The conductances of the complexes were measured in DMF using a Systronic conductivity bridge. The data are stated in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the complexes correspond to the composition CrOClL₂, where L stands the organic ligand. Low molar conductance values of 2 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicate nonelectrolytic nature of the complexes. A single spot in tlc supports the discrete nature of the Cr^V complexes.

The epr spectra of the powder samples exhibit a single line signal at room temperature without any hyperfine splitting (Fig. 1). The calculated <g_{av}> values were around 2.03 indicating the presence of one unpaired electron.

Fig. 1. Epr spectra of complexes at room temperature: (...) CrOCl (pipdtc)₂, (-) CrOCl (dedtc)₂ and (- - -) CrOCl (morpdtc)₂.

The electronic spectra in dichloromethane of the complexes show three bands around 260, 490

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)			ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)				<g> _{av}
	N	S	Cr	C-N	Cr-O	Cr-S	Cr-Cl	
CrOCl (dedtc) ₂	8.19 (7.01)	32.45 (32.08)	12.88 (13.01)	1 500s	900s	540s	370s	2.04
CrOCl (morpdtc) ₂	7.00 (6.55)	28.79 (29.99)	12.00 (12.16)	1 475s	1 020s	510m	360s	2.03
CrOCl (pipdtc) ₂	7.09 (6.58)	29.78 (30.27)	12.46 (12.28)	1 480s	1 010s	510s	360s	2.03

*dedtc = C₆H₁₀NS₂, morpdtc = C₆H₉ONS₂, pipdtc = C₆H₁₀NS₂.